

Soil and crop management

Effect of nitrogen levels and application time on direct-sown rice

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Direct sown Kranti (1981) and Ratna (1982) were tested for response to 20, 40, 60, or 80 kg N/ha applied at sowing, interculture by country plow, tillering, or panicle initiation at Sarkanda Farm, Bilaspur. Soil was a sandy loam with

180-87-436 kg available NPK/ha in 1981 and 100-65-622 kg available NPK/ha in 1982.

Drought limited response to fertilizer in 1981, but different N application levels significantly affected number of tillers/plant, panicle length, and filled spikelets for Kranti. N application did not significantly affect those characters for Ratna. Application of 80 kg N/ha increased yield significantly over that of other treatments, which yielded similarly (see table).

Applications of N at sowing, interculture, or as four splits (sowing, intercul-

ture, tillering, and panicle initiation) produced similar results. Application of N in equal splits at sowing and interculture, interculture and tillering, and ½ at interculture and equal splits at tillering and panicle initiation produced similarly and yielded significantly more tillers than other treatments (see table). Grain yield was significantly more when N was applied at interculture, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Yields tended to be low because incidence of gall midge, bacterial blight, and sheath rot was high. □

Effect of nitrogen levels and application time on yield-contributing characters and rice yield, Bilaspur, India.

Treatment	Kranti, 1981				Ratna, 1982			
	Effective tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers (no./plant)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets (no./panicle)	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Nitrogen (kg/ha)</i>								
20	2.3	20	14	3.1	2.2	20	22	2.2
40	2.6	21	13	3.2	2.4	21	17	2.4
60	2.7	20	10	3.2	2.4	20	22	2.4
80	2.8	21	9	3.4	2.7	22	17	2.8
CD (0.05)	0.2	1	2	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.3
<i>Application time</i>								
At sowing	2.4	20	11	2.9	2.2	21	16	2.0
At interculture	2.5	20	11	3.2	2.4	21	23	2.5
Equal splits at sowing and interculture	2.8	20	10	3.2	2.5	20	17	2.4
Equal splits at interculture and tillering	2.7	20	12	3.3	2.4	21	24	2.5
½ N at interculture, ¼ at tillering, and ¼ at panicle initiation	2.7	21	12	3.5	2.5	21	20	2.8
Equal splits at sowing, interculture, tillering, and panicle initiation	2.4	21	12	3.2	2.3	21	16	2.6
CD (0.05)	0.3	ns	ns	ns	ns	1	5	0.3

^a ns = nonsignificant.

Paddy and air-breathing-fish culture: effects of supplemental feed on the growth and yield of rice and fish

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We studied the effects of supplemental feed on growth and yield of mixed

cultures of two air-breathing catfishes Singhi (*Hereropnaustes fossilis*) and Magur (*Clarias batrachus*) and scented rice variety Randhunipagal at ORP in aman season.

The experiment consisted of these treatments: 1) control (rice plots without fish), 2) rice plot with fish, and 3) rice plot with fish and artificial feed.

Equal numbers of Magur and Singhi fingerlings were stocked at 1 fish/m² in early Oct. Before stocking, they were

treated with a 100 ppm solution of formalin for 30 s. Each morning, fish in treatment 3 were fed a low-cost 1:2 mixture of fishmeal and rice bran mixed with cow dung at 5% total body weight. Fish were harvested by draining the plots in mid-Nov.

Plots were 24 × 6 m with a shallow 75 × 40-cm perimeter canal. A trapezoidal protective dike bounded the canal.

Rice was sown on 10 Jul (midmonsoon). Seedlings were transplanted in wet